

A preliminary study on the effect of dose rate on 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan, L-cysteine and cystamine Ψ

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Dose rate dependent expositions of chromophores like SH, COOH and NH₂ occurred with L-cysteine (0.4 mM) that were detected by increase in absorbance intensity at absorbance maximum. Depletion of these chromophores as a function of increasing dose of irradiation were detected by specific reagents. No significant dependence of dose rate on exposition of chromophores were observed with cystamine (1 mM). But depletion of SH and NH₂ groups as an increasing function of dose from it were confirmed by specific reagents. Dose rate dependency in the exposition of chromophores of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (25, μ M) was observed. Depletion of NH₂ and COOH groups with increasing radiation dose was confirmed by specific reagents.

5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan interacts with DNA and nucleohistone¹. The radiolytic degradation products of the compound are known². Its LD₅₀ (30) value has been reported³ to be 610 mg/kg. L-Cysteine has been found to give no toxic effect for human beings at a dose of 16000 μ M/kg/day⁴. Its dose reduction factor (DRF) has been reported to be 1.19 for ⁶⁰Co gamma rays with male mice⁵. Cystamine give good radioprotection (DRF = 1.65) against ⁶⁰Co gamma irradiation for adult rats⁶.

Mechanism of radioprotection for all these compounds are by scavenging of hydroxyl radicals by amino groups⁷. Radioprotective efficacy and mechanism of action of cysteine and cystamine singly or in combination have also been reported⁸. Various techniques like HPLC⁹, DNA binding studies¹⁰, net charge¹¹ on these thiols are used as determining factors for elucidation of protection mechanism. But the effect of dose rate on the depletion of amino, thiol and carboxylic acid groups *in vitro* in solution for these compounds have not yet been studied. Hence the present study in connection with radioprotection has been explored.

Results and discussion

L-Cysteine (conc. 0.4 mM) was irradiated to different doses up to 100 Gy at two dose rates (1.52 and 0.009 Gy/s). The unirradiated compound showed an absorption maximum at 218–220 nm. At a higher dose rate (i.e. 1.52 Gy/s) with increase in dose. There was a consistent increase in absorption intensity at $A_{\lambda_{max}}$. There was a red-shift in the position of absorption maximum. There was a consistent increase in pH (from 6.46 to 7.63) with dose. Moreover, there was a linear increase in $A_{\lambda_{max}}$ with increase in dose (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. UV absorption spectra of L-cysteine in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states (conc., 0.4 mM; dose rate, 1.52 Gy/s; pH range 6.46–7.63): (O) unirrad. pH 6.46; (□) 20 Gy, pH 6.80; (Δ) 30 Gy, pH 7.50; (●) 80 Gy, pH 7.40; (⊙) 100 Gy, pH 7.63. Inset: Absorbance intensity at absorption maximum as a function of dose of gamma irradiation.

At a lower dose rate (i.e. 0.009 Gy/s) a biphasic variation in absorbance intensity at absorbance maximum was observed with increase in dose. Below 50 Gy there was almost no change, but above 50 Gy, $A_{\lambda_{max}}$ increased with dose. Slight increase in pH (from 6.46 to 7.51) with increase in dose was observed. Irradiated L-cysteine showed liberation of sulfur dioxide, ammonia and carbon dioxide. All these could be detected within an absorbed dose of 100 Gy (Fig. 2).

The absorption maximum at 218–220 nm is due to NH₂-

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Fig. 2. UV absorption spectra of L-cysteine in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states (conc., 0.4 mM; dose rate, 0.009 Gy/s; pH range, 6.46–7.51) : (O) unir. pH 6.46, (□) 40 Gy, pH 6.90, (●) 60 Gy, pH 7.20; (⊗) 80 Gy, pH 7.51. Inset : Absorbance intensity at absorption maximum as a function of dose of gamma irradiation.

$\text{CH}_2\text{-CO}_2\text{H}$ chromophore. The increase in absorbance intensity accompanied by red-shift with dose is due to the formation of free auxochromes like SH groups in solution¹².

At lower dose rate (i.e. 0.009 Gy/s) up to 50 Gy, proportional increase of chromophores does not take place due to energy transduction through L-cysteine. But at higher rates (1.52 Gy/s) linear dose-response relationship is a clear indication of availability of increasing number of free chromophores in the solution. Moreover, intermolecular interaction occurred at low dose rate thereby forming CONH groups which show an absorption maximum at 217–225 nm¹². The bond energies¹³ of C–SH, C–NH₂ and C–COOH are 62.0, 69.7 and 83.1 kcal mol⁻¹. If the molecules of L-cysteine remain free in solution then with increasing dose ease of bond breakage is C–SH > C–NH₂ > C–COOH. The overall reactions produce resultant increase in pH (i.e. formation of H₂SO₃, H₂CO₃ and NH₄OH).

Cystamine (conc. 1 mM) showed an absorption maximum at 245 nm¹². When 1 mM cystamine was irradiated to different doses up to 100 Gy at the dose rates of 0.009 and 1.49 Gy/s, a slight increase in $A_{245\text{nm}}$ values were observed at higher dose rate. The decrease in pH values were also of the same magnitude (i.e. 6.21 for unirradiated to 5.90 for 100 Gy) for both the dose rates. Irradiated cystamine (1 mM, 100 Gy) showed liberation of sulfur dioxide and ammonia.

Radiation-induced degradation of the compound will take place first at C–S bond and then at C–NH₂ bond as the bond energies are 62.0 and 69.7 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. Protons from SH groups formed are imparted to solution more compared to the formation of ammonia. This resulted in decrease of pH¹⁴.

It is known¹⁵ that 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5HTP)

shows two absorption maxima and a shoulder at 207, 275 and 220 nm, respectively. Dose rate dependency was observed for 5HTP (conc. 25 μM) in its absorbance values at 207 and 275 nm for the dose rates of 1.48 and 0.009 Gy/s.

The absorbance values are more for each dose at higher dose rate compared to that at lower dose rate. For a dose of 100 Gy there was decrease in pH (unirradiated 6.48 and irradiated 5.57). 5HTP showed liberation of ammonia and carbon dioxide when irradiated (conc. 25 μM, dose 100 Gy).

Dose rate dependency at 207 and 275 nm for 5HTP indicates that exposition of chromophores at 207 (i.e. pyrrole) and 275 nm (i.e. side-chain) takes place to different extents. It is more at higher dose rate and less at lower dose rate.

Formation of these chromophores is by depletion of original compound as a result of energy transduction which is dose rate dependent. The decrease in pH (from 6.48 to 5.57) is due to depletion of COOH which far exceeds the formation of ammonia as $G(\text{NH}_3) < 0.5$ (Ref. 16). It has been reported that hydroxyl radical attack is more severe than that produced by other radiolysis products of water¹⁷.

Experimental

L-Cysteine, cystamine dihydrochloride and 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (Sigma) were used. Their stock solutions were prepared in water, from which required concentration of each solution was made. Aliquots of these solutions (8 ml) were placed in a series of glass tubes (thickness 1 mm × 2 cm i.d.). These were irradiated in Gamma Cell 220 and Gamma chamber 5000 at dose rates of 0.009 and 1.48–1.52 Gy/s, respectively, as determined by FBX¹⁸ and Fricke¹⁹ dosimetry. Absorption spectra were measured on a GBC 916 spectrophotometer. pH was measured on a Toshniwal CL-46 pH meter. Formations of ammonia, carbon dioxide and sulfur dioxide were detected by Nessler's reagent, decolourization of alkaline phenolphthalein and red colour formation by use of potassium ferrocyanide-zinc sulfate-sodium nitroprusside reagent, respectively.

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Upadhyay *et al.* : A preliminary study on the effect of dose rate on 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan, L-cysteine *etc.*

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